

Assessment, Development and Validation of Programmed-Instructional-Package for Teaching Basic-Technology among upper Basic School Students in Gusau Metropolis, Zamfara State

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Abstract

This study employed a developmental research type design. The development involved the 5 stages of a model; these are Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation and Evaluation (ADDIE) model. Purposive sampling technique was used to select five Basic Technology teachers from two Upper Basic Schools in Gusau with a minimum of eight years of teaching experience and computer literacy and 45 Upper Basic 9 Basic Technology students. The data collected was analysed using mean and standard deviation. The findings of this study revealed that the Educational Technology experts agreed that the package was user-friendly and suitable for learning as a result the average mean responses of 3.64 by them. Also, the findings of this study further revealed that almost all the teachers of Basic Technology were willing to teach through the use of the Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) because of its effectiveness with the average mean of responses of 3.82 which indicated that Basic Technology teachers agreed that the PIP was very effective for teaching and learning Basic Technology. This study concluded that the use of the package by the students is more preferable to teachers. This study recommended among others that the students should explore the opportunities offered by PIP for revision as well as for individualized learning; teachers should develop and utilize PIP for teaching Basic Technology concepts so as to increase teachers' knowledge on new innovations in ICT-Based instructional strategies.

Keywords: ADDIE, PIP, Basic Technology, Development, Validation.

Introduction

Basic Technology as a subject introduces learners to basic rudiments of skills and also one of the subjects in the curriculum which is taken by all students in Upper Basic Schools in Nigeria. Basic Technology is stated as a subject that helps in the technological growth of a nation (Bamiro & Akuru, 2015). It combines so many skilled subjects at their basic levels out of which learners can make career in technological area. The curriculum is so structured for students to choose a career after the last year of the basic education to function in society as artisans and craftsmen (Babafemi, 2020).

The three main objectives of teaching Basic Technology as stated by Nigeria Educational Research Development Council (NERDC, 2007) is to inculcate technology literacy, that is, basic understanding of, and capability in technology; expose students to the society to match their talents and interest for wise vocational choice; and also to inculcate positive attitude towards work as the basis of human identity, livelihood and power. Thus, it is obvious that Basic Technology which is a core subject of the 9-3-4 System of Education practised in Nigeria today involves the academic and practical study of materials and source of energy with the whole purpose of providing a broad based skills development approach to practical oriented work, where practical skills are needs. It also involves making immediate environment more conducive for continual survival of human race. This subject is expected to prepare learners for skilled subjects. Basic Technology is also an integrated study of skilled subjects such as woodwork, metalwork, building technology, auto-mechanic, electrical or electronics, ceramics and technical drawing (Onyesolu & Eze, 2017).

Bamiro and Akuru (2015) observed that studying Basic Technology will afford one to acquire the knowledge and skills to understand how and what will lead to economic development of the community. They stressed further that knowledge acquired

from Basic Technology can be applied to all aspect of human life such as religion, transportation, communication, medicine, business, politics, social, academics and others, since technology is an essential tool for national development as well as an instrument for preparing the youth to face the unfolding tasks of the contemporary age. Greg (2015) opined that knowledge empowers students with talents and approaches necessary for their success in contemporary knowledge society.

In programmed instruction (PI), contents are presented to learners in an arranged order of organized paces. Learners are then expected to toil through the automated content individually. Their comprehension will be tested by reacting to questions or filling in a blank space. They are then immediately shown the correct answer or given additional information. It is a notable fact that computers and teaching machines are often used to present the material; books may be utilized in some situations (Mangal, & Mangal, 2018).

Programmes are also sequences of information which may be verbal, visual, audio or audio-visual designed to elicit predetermined response. It is the process by which learner's construction of ideas is supported. The theory underlying modern programmed instruction was based primarily on research conducted by an American psychologist called Skinner in 1954 (Mangal & Mangal, 2018). The instructional sequence is established with computer programmes for learners. In this aspect, facts necessary for a particular instruction might be obtainable in bits. The instructional sequence is developed through a form of computer programme for learners. The degree of accuracy with which the learner responds will determine whether the learner will progress afterward, review the bit or take the previous study earlier presented (Abimbade, 2010).

In programmed learning, students participate in the assessment stage. Greece (2015) affirmed that PIP promotes student-centred learning, because students can construct their own conceptualizations and find solutions to problems, mastering autonomy and independence. The emphasis is on the learner rather than the teacher. It is the learner who interacts with his or her environment and thus gains an understanding of its features and characteristics. Mangal and Mangal (2018) highlighted the rationale behind the use of Programmed Instructional Package as a strategy for instruction most particularly in secondary schools. Firstly, when students are motivated they put in more effort and they are ready to make connections. Programmed Instructional Package uses several strategies to surge learners' incentive; the second feature is to increase students' motivation. Students can directly learn with the use of package based on the cues to ascertain the selection of correct answers. Lastly, the answers are given to serve as immediate feedback that encourage learning.

The Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation (ADDIE) model explains logical method to instructional content design. Advocates of this model claimed that the process of designing instructional package can be carried out more efficiently and effectively if the steps are followed in a logical order so that the output of each step provides the input to the next.

Figure 1: Core elements of Instructional Design

Source: Gustafson and Branch (2002)

Basic Technology as a subject is considered as unique key for sustainable development of any nation (Bamiro & Akuru, 2015). Experience has shown that there are problems facing the teaching of this subject in various Upper Basic Schools as a result of unqualified teachers, ill-equipped workshops, outdated reading materials, attitudes of parents

towards the subject, insufficient time allocation for the practical, epileptic power supply to run the machinery for practical (Adeniran, 2018).

Adegbija (2016) and Asadu and Ameh (2017) noted that the methods used by most of the teachers in teaching students in schools is one of the major constraints in achieving goals of studying Basic Technology as a subject in Upper Basic Schools. They attributed these problems to lack of adequate knowledge in the skills and poor strategies for teaching because teachings nowadays are mostly teacher-centred rather than student-centred.

This investigation was carried out to develop and validate a PIP for teaching Basic Technology in Upper Basic Schools in Nigeria using ADDIE model to determine the accessibility, cost implications, teaching and learning functions, interactivity, organisational issues and novelty.

Objectives of the study

The main purpose of this study was to assess, develop and validate a Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) for teaching Basic Technology in Upper Basic Schools in Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Specifically, the study was to:

1. Validate the Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) developed by the experts.
2. Determine the effectiveness of the Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) for teaching selected topics in the Basic Technology in Upper Basic School.
3. Assess the effect of the developed PIP based on gender.

Research Questions

The following research questions were generated to guide this study:

1. How did experts validate the PIP developed?
2. What is the effectiveness of the developed PIP on students taught with the package and those taught using the conventional method?
3. What is the effect of gender on the effectiveness of the Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) developed?

Methodology

The research design used was a developmental research type. The study considered this research type to carry out the development and validation of a PIP for teaching Basic Technology in Upper Basic Schools in Nigeria. The development involved the 5 stages of a model; these are Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation and Evaluation (ADDIE) model. The population of this study consisted of all Basic Technology teachers in Upper Basic Schools and all Upper Basic 9 Basic Technology students in Upper Basic Schools in Zamfara State, Nigeria. The sample selected for this research were five Basic Technology teachers from two Upper Basic Schools in Gusau with a minimum of eight years of teaching experience and computer literacy and 45 Upper Basic 9 Basic Technology students. The investigation involved the use of researcher's adapted questionnaire to elicit needed responses from subject matter experts (Basic Technology teachers), Educational Technology experts and the students who evaluated the Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) in terms of accessibility, teaching and learning, interactivity and user-friendliness.

Furthermore, it was used to determine the effectiveness of the package on learners' achievement on Basic Technology, a quasi-experimental procedure (pre-test, post-test, experimental and control group) that involved the use of two levels of independent variables. The independent variables are the Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) and the Conventional Basic Technology Teaching (CBTT) while the dependent variable is the post-test performance of the students in Basic Technology. Both experimental and control groups were administered with the pre-test and post-test on Basic Technology Achievement Test (BTAT). Experimental Group was subjected to treatment using the package developed while the Control Group was taught using BTAT. The design layout is as shown in table 2

Table 1: Experimental procedure layout

Groups	Pretest	Treatment	Posttest
Experimental Group	O ₁	PIP	O ₂
Control Group	O ₃	Conventional Basic Technology Teaching	O ₄

The schematic representation of this research layout is as shown below:

Where,

- O₁ represents the Pre-testing of the Experimental Group,
- O₂ represents the Post-testing of the Experimental Group,
- O₃ represents the Pre-testing of the Control Group,
- O₄ represents the Post-testing of the Control Group.
- X₁ represents the Treatment (Programmed Instructional Package) for the Experimental Group,
- X₂ represents the Conventional Basic Technology Teaching for the Control Group,

The reports from each of the stages of usability of the package were written down and was analysed to find out if the Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) developed is effective or suitable for excellent utilization in Basic Technology subject. Responses from various experts were collected and analysed using mean and standard deviation. A four-point Likert rating of Strongly Agree (4 Points), Agree (3 Points), Disagree (2 Points) and Strongly Disagree (1 Point) were also used in weighing responses to items in the checklist. A mean response below 2.50 was considered as benchmark for Disagree while a mean response of 2.50 and above was considered as benchmark for Agree. Responses to checklist items meant for answering research questions 1-3 were analysed by using mean and standard deviation.

Results

RQ 1: How did experts rate the Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) developed?

After the package had been effectively designed, developed and produced, they were subjected to expert judgment during which the package were qualitatively and quantitatively assessed. During the qualitative assessment, positive comments were made by assessors which confirmed that the package was suitable and appropriate for the purpose for which it was meant for. The qualitative of the assessment, a 10 item rating scale was administered to five Educational Technology experts.

The results of their assessment of the instructional package is presented in Table 2

Table 2: Mean rating scale of educational technology experts on the PIP developed

S/No	Statement	N	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	S.D	Decision
1	The package is suitable for learning	5	03	02	00	00	4.40	0.55	Agree
2	The modules in the package are simple for comprehension	5	04	01	00	00	3.40	0.55	Agree
3	There is uniformity among illustrations embedded in to the package	5	04	01	00	00	3.80	0.45	Agree
4	Animation incorporated into package provides better opportunity for learning.	5	01	04	00	00	3.20	0.45	Agree
5	The package lay emphasis on the key concepts of the subject	5	04	01	00	00	3.80	0.45	Agree
6	The colour incorporated into the graphic illustrations provides better opportunity for learning	5	02	03	00	00	3.40	0.55	Agree
7	The content of these lessons interesting	5	04	01	00	00	3.80	0.45	Agree
8	The task conforms to standard and is sequentially arranged	5	02	03	00	00	3.40	0.55	Agree
9	The sound incorporated into task is clear	5	04	01	00	00	3.80	0.45	Agree
10	The fonts and graphical illustrations are legible	5	01	04	00	00	3.40	0.55	Agree
Grand Mean							3.64		Agree

Table 2 reveals that all the Educational Technology experts confirmed that the Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) was suitable and appropriate for the purpose for which it was meant for. The mean response of the Educational Technology experts to each of the ten items was above 2.50 while the averages mean experts' responses of all the items were 3.64. This indicates that the Educational Technology experts agreed that the package was user-friendly and suitable for learning.

RQ 2: What is the effectiveness of the developed Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) on students taught in selected topics with developed package and those taught using the conventional method?

After the package had been effectively designed, developed and produced, they were subjected to Basic Technology teachers' judgment during which the package was used in teaching for qualitatively and quantitatively assessed.

During the qualitative assessment, positive comments were made by assessors which confirmed that the package was suitable and appropriate for the purpose for which it was meant for. The qualitative of the assessment, a 24 item rating scale was administered to five Basic Technology teachers in Upper Basic schools in Zamfara state, Nigeria.

Table 3: Mean rating scale of basic technology teachers on the effectiveness of PIP

S/No	Statement	N	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	S.D	Decision
1	The concept of Programmed Instructional Package is a new idea in my school	5	03	02	00	00	3.60	0.55	Agree
2	Programmed Instructional Package is new to basic technology students.	5	02	03	00	00	3.40	0.55	Agree
3	All students in Upper Basic III have access to computer laboratory	5	00	01	02	02	1.80	0.84	Disagree
4	Log in into Programmed Instructional Package is not difficult to all students	5	00	00	02	03	1.80	0.84	Disagree
5	Students can access Programmed Instruction Package with or without network connection	5	04	01	00	00	3.80	0.45	Agree
6	The contents of the lesson in the packages are academically relevant	5	01	04	00	00	3.20	0.45	Agree
7	Navigation on the package from one module to another module is very accurate.	5	05	00	00	00	4.00	0.00	Agree
8	The method of teaching match students' need.	5	01	04	00	00	3.20	0.45	Agree
9	The subject matter in the package is in line with the Basic technology curriculum.	5	05	00	00	00	4.00	0.00	Agree
10	Questions asked after each of the scripts measures the knowledge acquisition	5	03	02	00	00	3.60	0.55	Agree
11	The modules in the package are simple for Comprehension	5	03	02	00	00	3.60	0.55	Agree
12	Questions asked after each of the scripts measures the knowledge acquisition	5	02	03	00	00	3.40	0.55	Agree
13	I retain the material in the lessons because of sound embedded into presentation	5	01	04	00	00	3.20	0.45	Agree
14	Cue on each question helps me to implement the teaching strategy.	5	04	01	00	00	3.80	0.45	Agree
15	The sound attached to the presentation provided better opportunity for learning	5	02	03	00	00	3.40	0.55	Agree
16	My feelings about the sound presentation in these lessons are positive	5	03	02	00	00	3.60	0.55	Agree
17	Reinforcement of the learning outcome is automatic	5	03	02	00	00	3.60	0.55	Agree
18	Graphics used serve as appropriate purpose level for students.	5	03	02	00	00	3.60	0.55	Agree
19	With adequate facilities, the use of the package will be effective for learning	5	05	00	00	00	4.00	0.00	Agree
20	The use of package does not require teacher as an instructional mediator	5	01	00	04	00	2.40	0.99	Disagree
21	Illustrations in the package are meaningful.	5	04	00	01	00	2.80	0.45	Agree
22	Lip readings are in the same line with the sound.	5	01	04	00	00	3.20	0.45	Agree
23	The package may be too expensive for use in the schools	5	02	03	00	00	3.00	1.22	Agree
24	Teachers will need training on the use of package as a learning tool	5	00	03	02	00	2.60	0.55	Agree
Grand Mean							3.28		Agree

Table 3 reveals that almost all the teachers of Basic Technology were willing to teach through the use of the Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) in selected topics in Basic Technology because of its effectiveness. The respondents agreed to all the 24 items with mean responses was above 2.50 with exception of items 3, 4 and 20 that were below the bench mark of 2.50. The average mean of responses to all the items was 3.82 which were above the bench mark. This indicates that Basic Technology teachers agreed that the PIP was very effective for teaching and learning Basic Technology.

RQ 3: What is the interaction effect of students on the effectiveness of the Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) developed?

During the qualitative assessment, positive comments were made by the students confirmed that the package was suitable and appropriate for the purpose for which it was meant for. The qualitative of the assessment, a 14 item rating scale was administered to Basic Technology students in Upper Basic schools in Zamfara state, Nigeria in line with Dick, Carey and Carey (2005) recommendations.

The summary of the assessment of the Programmed Instructional Package by the respondents is presented in Table 4;

Table 5: Mean rating scale of validation on student’s reactions on the effectiveness of PIP

S/No	Statement	N	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	S.D	Decision
1	I tend to develop more interest in the lesson content because of the combination of sound in the instructional process.	45	27	18	00	00	3.60	0.50	Agree
2	Every expectation I have for this lesson has been ignited.	45	08	28	07	02	2.99	0.72	Agree
3	The package is very boring as a result of inability to proceed to the next question if the selection is not correct.	45	09	17	11	08	2.60	1.01	Agree
4	This lesson had not met the hope I had for it	45	06	11	17	11	2.27	0.99	Disagree
5	Using PIP presentation for the lesson helped me to have a better learning experience.	45	35	10	00	00	3.78	0.42	Agree
6	The contents of the lessons are dull	45	01	07	15	22	1.71	0.82	Disagree
7	The presentation used in this lesson leaves a lot to be desired.	45	14	23	07	01	3.11	0.75	Disagree
8	I find the content of these lessons interesting.	45	30	14	01	00	3.64	0.53	Agree
9	The knowledge of the lesson is retained because of PIP presentation.	45	25	16	04	00	3.49	0.66	Agree
10	Seeing the lessons on PIP offer a reality of experience which stimulates self-activity on the part of student.	45	22	16	02	00	3.44	0.59	Agree
11	The PIP presentation provided little opportunity for learning.	45	10	12	16	07	2.71	0.82	Agree
12	The content in the lessons had not met the standard compare to textbooks.	45	04	09	18	14	2.07	0.94	Disagree
13	My feelings about the PIP presentation in these lessons are positive.	45	21	22	01	01	3.40	0.65	Agree
14	These lessons helped me to see the complexities of PIP and instructional system design (ISD).	45	23	20	01	01	3.44	0.66	Agree
Gran Mean			3.02		Agree				

Table 5 reveals that the students agreed with the effectiveness of PIP as a result of their mean responses on each of the 14 items that were above the bench mark of 2.50 with exception to only items 4, 6 and 12 that were below the bench mark of 2.50. The average mean of responses to all the items is 3.02 which were above the bench mark.

Though, the use of the Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) may be slow down and waste the time of a student with a very low intelligent quotient as the bulk of the work will be on them always, hence, the use of the package is more preferable to teacher dominating class because this method affords students to be more empowered and remove fear as they interact with the computer. They believe that they learn faster and better with the use of Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) for learning.

Not only that, a shy student can feel free with the student's centred learning environment because the level of knowledge acquisition can also be improved. The use of Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) tests the student's ability and marks their progress. It gives room for active participation of the learner. Since the developed Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) is meant to be in teaching Basic Technology in Upper Basic Schools in Nigeria, the responses from both teachers and students are very vital.

Conclusion

The result obtained from the data gathered and analyzed in this study indicated that the developed Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) on Basic Technology concepts met with the standard required when evaluated with rubrics after being exposed to experts. The result also showed that the developed Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) covers the required Basic Technology concepts, the percentage of the evaluators was impressive and the task contained in the Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) comports with the standard question and they were sequentially arranged.

The developed Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) was used and found effective for learning Basic Technology concepts. The students taught using Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) performed better than their counterparts taught using conventional instructional mode. The findings in the research also established that students have positive attitude towards developed Programmed Instructional Package (PIP). According to the result in this study, the developed Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) is a valuable instructional strategy that can be incorporated into Upper Basic schools to teach Basic Technology concepts. It pleases the students because they have autonomy as students to do their work. They were motivated to read resources provided in the Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) and also developed their thinking skills. Many preferred learning Basic Technology concepts using Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) to the teacher-centred approach because it was a different way of learning concept and it was both fun and challenging.

Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) therefore, brings about effective learning of Basic Technology concepts. This is an indication that it is an interesting and engaging alternative for learning. Students were able to solve problems and share points of view, construct the meaning of the text by bargaining it with their peers. The use of conventional instruction is gradually losing its acceptance, and teachings with antiquated materials are no more encouraged. It is hoped that the utilization of this Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) for learning Basic Technology concepts for Upper Basic students will allow better understanding of the concepts and improve students' performance in general

Recommendations

Based on the major findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Students should endeavour to explore the opportunities offered by Programmed Instructional Package (PIP). The package can be utilized for revision as well as for individualized learning because learning can still take place in the absence of teachers and user-friendly;
2. Teachers should endeavour to develop and utilize Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) for teaching Basic Technology concepts. This will further increase teachers' knowledge on new innovations in ICT-Based instructional strategies;
3. Basic technology teachers should expose the students to ICT-Based instructional strategies like Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) to promote students' autonomy to knowledge acquisition, discovery learning and student-centred instructional approach;
4. Educators should endeavour to see the endowed benefits of Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) in teaching and learning, since the application of Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) in teaching and learning Basic Technology concepts serves as a motivator which encourages students to have positive attitude towards their programme;

Suggestions for Further Studies

The following are suggestions for further research in this area:

1. Efforts to replicate this work for other concepts in Basic Technology. Such concepts are energy and power, building, applied electricity and electronics, maintenance, drawing practice etc. before the findings of this study can be generalised;
2. Efforts should be made to modify the Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) by correcting the shortcomings in order to ensure its effectiveness and perfection;
3. Further research is recommended in other disciplines to ascertain the effect of Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) on students' academic performance. This will further help to determine the efficacy of the instructional strategy;
4. The Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) can also be developed for all subjects at both Lower and Upper Basic schools; and the effectiveness of the modified Programmed Instructional Package (PIP) can be administered on Upper Basic Schools Basic Technology students in other parts of the country.

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